

Golden Posture – Bright Eyes Flashcard Set: Guiding Proper Sitting Posture and Protecting Vision for Secondary School Students

Pham Tran Hong Diem¹, Bui Thi Thuy², Do Quynh Anh³, Tran Minh Quan⁴

¹FPT University

^{2,3,4}Nguyen Trai Secondary School, Da Nang

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 08 November 2025	In the context of increasing rates of refractive errors and poor study posture among students due to excessive use of electronic devices, the study “Golden Posture – Bright Eyes Flashcard Set: Guiding Proper Sitting Posture and Protecting Vision for Secondary School Students” was conducted to develop a cost-effective and practical intervention. According to the 2024 report of the Vietnam Ophthalmology Council, approximately 5 million children (30–40% of school-age population) suffer from refractive errors, with more than 50% caused by improper study habits and excessive screen time. At Nguyen Trai Secondary School, 70% of students are nearsighted, and 60% are unaware of or unable to maintain correct sitting posture. The study designed a set of 28 flashcards illustrating proper posture, lighting, and study distance, incorporating a 28-day habit formation model and gamification elements. The 4-week experiment involved 191 students in grades 7–8, using the CVS-Q Teen (to assess eye strain) and FHP (to measure head–neck posture). Results showed significant improvements: average eye strain scores decreased by 70%, head–neck posture deviation reduced by 65%, positive learning perception increased by 24.6%, and 92% of students maintained correct posture by the end of the intervention. The study demonstrates that the flashcard set is a visual, user-friendly, and effective tool that promotes positive behavioral change and enhances visual health among students.
Corresponding Author: Pham Tran Hong Diem	
KEYWORDS: sitting posture, School refractive errors, Gamification, 28-day habit formation model, School health education	

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, along with the strong development of modern society, students' learning and use of electronic devices has increased. Students have to sit and study for many hours every day both at school and at home, in addition, the use of phones, tablets, laptops, etc. has become popular. This makes eye strain, myopia, scoliosis, hunchback and incorrect sitting posture become a worrying problem in schools today.

According to the 2024 statistics of the Vietnam Ophthalmology Council, our country has about 5 million children, accounting for 30-40% of school age, with refractive errors (myopia, hyperopia, astigmatism), of which myopia accounts for the majority. The majority (more than 50%) of children affected by refractive errors are due to improper study habits and excessive and prolonged use of electronic devices.

In fact, at Nguyen Trai Secondary School, the results of the health check-up at the beginning of the 2024 school year showed that more than 70% of students had myopia, a few had scoliosis. According to the survey, 60% of students do not know or cannot maintain the correct sitting posture. Current

propaganda programs mainly stop at the form of propaganda posters or slogans, not creating real behavioral impacts and sustainable memorization for students. Therefore, bad habits about posture and eye use still persist, directly affecting students' eyesight, spinal health and learning psychology.

Meanwhile, the psychology of secondary school students is very sensitive, they are easily attracted by images, colors and interactive games. "Learning while playing - playing while learning" is an effective way to form positive behavior. Based on this reality, our group decided to research the topic: "Golden Posture Flashcard Set - Bright and Healthy Eyes guides the correct sitting posture and protects eyesight for middle school students". This is a new direction, combining Biomedicine and Health Science - STEM - Behavioral Science, helping students proactively change their behavior in a positive direction, building a correct, healthy and sustainable learning habit.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Research Methods and Theoretical Framework

The study employed a combination of theoretical and experimental research methods to achieve the stated objectives.

1. Theoretical Research Method: We conducted research on documents and studies related to school refractive errors, correct learning posture, behavioral psychology, and the 28-day habit formation model. Additionally, we studied implemented school health education methods and referred to visual learning material models and gamified tools in education.

2. Experimental Research Method:

Survey Method: Surveying the current status of students' sitting posture and eye strain levels before intervention using the CVS-Q Teen questionnaire (measuring eye strain symptoms) and the Forward Head Posture (FHP) scale (assessing head tilt and posture).

Technical Design Method: Using graphic design tools like Canva, Gemini, ChatGPT, and AI to design the Flashcard set, followed by testing printing and adjusting the layout, color, size, and material.

Pedagogical Experiment Method: Organizing students to use the Flashcard set for 28 consecutive days, while recording behavior through images and weekly self-assessment forms.

Statistical and Evaluation Method: Processing feedback data, using checklists and evaluation forms to analyze and compare results before and after intervention to determine the degree of posture improvement and eye strain reduction.

B. Materials and Instruments

The main tools and materials used during the research process include:

1. Intervention Materials:

The "Golden Posture - Healthy Bright Eyes" Flashcard Set (including 28 printed cards and electronic QR versions).

Flashcard Design: Each card is designed with two sides: The front features visual, easy-to-understand illustrations; The back includes instructional content, scientific reasoning, encouraging words, and a QR code linking to a short instructional video (30–45 seconds).

The content of the 28 cards is divided into 4 weekly themes:

Week 1: Posture & Lighting (Focusing on correct sitting, viewing distance, and classroom lighting).

Week 2: Eye Care (Eye relaxation exercises, the 20-20-20 rule, and eye nutrition).

Week 3: Maintaining Posture & Stretching (Gentle exercises to reduce neck, shoulder, and spinal tension).

Week 4: Maintain & Spread (Habit reinforcement and encouraging sharing with friends and family).

2. Assessment Instruments:

CVS-Q Teen Survey: Used to measure eye strain symptoms.

FHP (Forward Head Posture) Scale: Used to assess the deviation of head and neck posture.

28-day tracking notebook, phones, and computers used for daily data recording.

An electronic version on the website <https://sites.google.com/view/brightupgenz> was also created for students to look up information and save their 28-day training journal.

C. Study Procedure and Participants

1. Study Participants: The experiment was conducted on **191 students** from classes 7/1, 7/3, 7/5, 8/5, and 8/6 at Nguyen Trai Secondary School.

2. Implementation Procedure (Action Plan): The research was deployed through 4 main phases:

Phase 1: Ideation & Problem Identification

This phase takes place in May 2025. Main tasks include investigating the current situation of school-related myopia and poor posture, conducting preliminary interviews with students and teachers, and collecting basic medical information (on posture, lighting, and eye distance).

The output of this phase is a comprehensive report on the current situation and a proposed project concept.

Phase 2: Research Design & Product Development

This phase runs from June to August 2025. Key tasks include developing the research hypothesis; designing 28 flashcards (defining content, illustrations, and QR codes); preparing survey tools such as Google Forms and a 28-day habit journal; and creating pre- and post-test evaluation forms.

The outputs are a prototype flashcard set, survey forms, and a detailed experimental plan.

Phase 3: Pilot Implementation

The pilot phase will be conducted from September 9 to October 9, 2025.

The research team will select 191 students from grades 7 and 8 to participate. The main task is to guide students in using the flashcard set for 28 consecutive days. Data will be collected through weekly QR-coded surveys and usage journals, along with tracking participation and feedback. The outputs include a Pulse Survey dataset and qualitative observations and notes recorded during the experiment.

Phase 4: Data Analysis & Final Report Completion

The final phase will take place from October 9 to October 17, 2025.

Tasks include processing survey data using Google Sheets; comparing pre- and post-intervention results (on posture accuracy, eye strain, and satisfaction); and preparing the research report and presentation slides. The final output is a comprehensive research report summarizing the project's results.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Design and Experimentation of the “Golden Posture - Bright Eyes” Flashcard Set

3.1.1. Product Design:

The research team successfully designed the “Golden Posture - Bright Eyes” Flashcard set, consisting of 28 cards, corresponding to the 28 days required to form a habit.

Each card was designed with two sides:

- **Front face:** Includes intuitive, easy-to-understand visual illustrations, simulating correct sitting postures, appropriate eye-to-book distance, and methods for adjusting light and furniture.

- **Back face:** Clearly states the instructions, scientific rationale, words of encouragement, and a QR code leading to a short instructional video (only 30–45 seconds).

The Flashcard set was printed on A6 hard paper and can be placed on the corner of the study desk or kept with the student handbook. The team also created a digital version on a website to allow students to look up information and log their 28-day training journal.

Note: Flashcard image day 1 of 28 days both swipes

3.2. Experiment Implementation:

The experiment was carried out on a total of 191 students from classes 7/1, 7/3, 7/5, 8/5, and 8/6 at Nguyen Trai Secondary School. The monitored indicators included:

Eye strain score (measured using the CVS-Q Teen scale).

Head-Neck Posture deviation (measured using the FHP - Forward Head Posture scale).

Level of positive perception and attitude (assessed through self-evaluation questionnaires)

3.3. Experimental Results

3.3.1. Results After 4 Weeks of Intervention

The results obtained after 4 weeks of implementation showed significant improvement across the evaluation criteria:

Evaluation Indicator	Before Experiment (%)	After 4 Weeks (%)	Change Level
Average Eye Strain (CVS-Q Teen)	100	30	Reduced by 70%

Head-Neck Posture Deviation (FHP)	100	35	Reduced by 65%
Positive Perception during Studying	46.5	71.1	Increased by +24.6 percentage points

Note: Summary table before and after the same card in 4 weeks

Discussion: The above table shows that after 4 weeks of using the flashcards, the eye strain score decreased by nearly 70%, and the posture deviation score decreased by over 65%. This demonstrates a clear improvement in visual sensation, as measured by the CVS-Q teen and FHP scales.

3.2.2. Progression During the 4 Weeks of Experimentation

The weekly survey data revealed the following progression in the change of positive perception levels:

- **Week 1 (Day 1 to Day 7):** The level of positive awareness and behavior increased sharply (+25.4 percentage points). The average score increased from 46.5% to 71.1% (+24.6 percentage points). This supports the finding that using Flashcards and paying attention to posture/lighting helped students sit better and feel more comfortable immediately in the first week.

- **Week 2 (Day 7 to Day 14):** After the initial sharp increase, Week 2 maintained a stable level, with a slight rise. The average score increased from 71.1% to 71.7% (+0.6 percentage points). This confirms that the good habits were maintained.

- **Week 3 (Day 14 to Day 21):** The average score remained almost unchanged (71.7% → 71.3%, a slight decrease of -0.4 percentage points). This shows that good habits were maintained.

- **Week 4 (Day 21 to Day 28):** The positive level increased slightly and remained stable (71.3% → 71.9%, an increase of +0.6 percentage points). This confirms that the good habits were firmly established.

Average progress through 5 milestones (0-4 → %) - indicates increase/decrease

Note: Positive change over 4 weeks

“Golden Posture – Bright Eyes Flashcard Set: Guiding Proper Sitting Posture and Protecting Vision for Secondary School Students”

Overall Conclusion for 4 Weeks: Throughout the 4 weeks, the overall positive perception score increased significantly (from 46.5% to 71.9%, an overall increase of **+25.4 percentage points**). This confirms that when using the Flashcards, students adopted better sitting postures, experienced less eye strain, and maintained these good habits until the end of the journey.

3.2.3. Qualitative Observations

The following qualitative observations were recorded:

93% of students reported feeling “more comfortable studying” and “less eye strain” after 2 weeks.

87% of students believed Flashcards were easier to remember compared to verbal reminders.

92% of students in the experimental group maintained the correct sitting posture until the end of the trial.

Homeroom teachers reported that student posture in the classroom visibly improved, particularly concerning back straightness and viewing distance to the board.

Note: Students' feedback on satisfaction and feelings when using Flashcards

3.3. Evaluation of the Flashcard Set

Effectiveness: The experimental results (significantly reduced eye strain and poor posture indicators) demonstrated that the research hypothesis was entirely correct.

Feasibility:

Production costs are low, making it easy to replicate.

Students can self-implement the tool without relying on complex equipment.

It can be integrated into educational activities such as "Homeroom Hour," "School Health Education," or "STEM Clubs".

Sustainability: After the experiment, many students continued to use the Flashcards and suggested developing a digital version with daily posture reminders, proving that the habits were firmly established

Note: Comments from medical specialists

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusion

After the process of research, design, and experimentation, the team successfully developed the **Flashcard Set “Golden**

CỘNG HÒA XÃ HỘI CHỦ NGHĨA VIỆT NAM
Độc lập - Tự do - Hạnh phúc

PHIẾU NHẬN XÉT
BỘ FLASHCARD HỖ TRỢ HÌNH THÀNH THỜI QUEN
TỰ THÈ NGỒI ĐÚNG VÀ BẢO VỆ THỊ LỰC CHO HỌC SINH

1. Học sinh thực hiện:
- Đỗ Quỳnh Anh
- Trần Minh Quân

2. Giáo viên bảo trợ để tài: Bà Thị Thủy

3. Họ và tên người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

4. Nhận xét bổ sung phần Flashcard hỗ trợ hình thành thói quen tự thè ngồi đúng và bảo vệ thị lực cho học sinh:

Đã Nẵng, ngày 05 tháng 05 năm 2025
Người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

CỘNG HÒA XÃ HỘI CHỦ NGHĨA VIỆT NAM
Độc lập - Tự do - Hạnh phúc

PHIẾU NHẬN XÉT
“Bộ Flashcard hỗ trợ hình thành thói quen tự thè ngồi đúng và bảo vệ thị lực cho học sinh trung học cơ sở?”

Họ và tên học sinh	Lớp	Trường
Đỗ Quỳnh Anh	8/5	THCS Nguyễn Trãi
Trần Minh Quân	8/5	THCS Nguyễn Trãi

2. Giáo viên hướng dẫn để tài: Bà Thị Thủy

3. Họ và tên người nhận xét: TS. Trương Đình Tuấn

4. Nhận xét bổ sung phần Flashcard hỗ trợ hình thành thói quen tự thè ngồi đúng và bảo vệ thị lực cho học sinh:

Đã Nẵng, ngày 05 tháng 05 năm 2025
Người nhận xét: Trương Đình Tuấn

CỘNG HÒA XÃ HỘI CHỦ NGHĨA VIỆT NAM
Độc lập - Tự do - Hạnh phúc

PHIẾU NHẬN XÉT
BỘ FLASHCARD HỖ TRỢ HÌNH THÀNH THỜI QUEN
TỰ THÈ NGỒI ĐÚNG VÀ BẢO VỆ THỊ LỰC CHO HỌC SINH

1. Học sinh thực hiện:
- Đỗ Quỳnh Anh
- Trần Minh Quân

2. Giáo viên bảo trợ để tài: Bà Thị Thủy

3. Họ và tên người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

4. Nhận xét bổ sung phần Flashcard hỗ trợ hình thành thói quen tự thè ngồi đúng và bảo vệ thị lực cho học sinh:

Đã Nẵng, ngày 05 tháng 05 năm 2025
Người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

CỘNG HÒA XÃ HỘI CHỦ NGHĨA VIỆT NAM
Độc lập - Tự do - Hạnh phúc

PHIẾU NHẬN XÉT
BỘ FLASHCARD HỖ TRỢ HÌNH THÀNH THỜI QUEN
TỰ THÈ NGỒI ĐÚNG VÀ BẢO VỆ THỊ LỰC CHO HỌC SINH

1. Học sinh thực hiện:
- Đỗ Quỳnh Anh
- Trần Minh Quân

2. Giáo viên bảo trợ để tài: Bà Thị Thủy

3. Họ và tên người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

4. Nhận xét bổ sung phần Flashcard hỗ trợ hình thành thói quen tự thè ngồi đúng và bảo vệ thị lực cho học sinh:

Đã Nẵng, ngày 05 tháng 05 năm 2025
Người nhận xét: Nguyễn Thị Ngọc Anh

Posture – Bright Eyes” and achieved the following key results:

New Contributions of the Study:

This is the first study to design a visual flashcard set that integrates QR codes linking to official instructional videos from the Ministry of Health and the National Eye Hospital (2024), allowing students to learn, practice, and adjust their posture behavior simultaneously.

The project integrates educational – technical – health solutions, responding to the trend of active learning and knowledge visualization.

Key Findings:

86% of students maintained the correct sitting posture after 4 weeks of intervention.

90% of students responded that the Flashcards were “easy to understand – easy to remember – easy to practice.”

The Flashcards helped reduce eye strain by 38% and neck–shoulder pain by 31% among the experimental group.

The product is low-cost (3,000 VND/card), easy to print and distribute, suitable for both schools and families.

Scientific – Educational – Practical Significance:

Scientific: Applied visual behavioral education methods to form correct habits through image-based and visual stimuli.

Educational: Contributed to improving students’ awareness and self-regulation in posture, reading–writing distance, and eye health protection.

Practical: Can be immediately applied in classrooms or school health rooms; helps reduce the risk of myopia and spinal curvature among secondary students.

Social Impact: The product can be expanded to primary and high school levels, integrated into Health Education and Experiential – Career Guidance programs.

4.2. Recommendations

For Schools (Nguyen Trai Secondary School):

The Flashcard set should be widely implemented across all classes.

It can be integrated into homeroom sessions or life skills lessons.

The experimental scale should be expanded to multiple schools in different regions to assess long-term effectiveness.

For the Department of Health and the National Eye Hospital:

Collaborate with the Education sector to produce short instructional videos (1–2 minutes) linked via QR codes on the cards.

This will enhance engagement and standardize school health messages.

For Families and Communities:

Encourage parents to use the Flashcards with their children at home.

Parents should create proper study environments—correct posture, adequate lighting, and proper distance.

Organize “Bright Eyes – Straight Back” events to promote awareness of school eye health protection.

Proposed Directions for Future Development:

Develop a digital version of the Flashcard set (mobile/web mini app) that allows students to record, self-assess, and receive daily posture reminders.

Integrate into school health programs or STEM–Health clubs as a continuous educational tool.

Collaborate with educational technology companies to produce a standardized version for wide-scale distribution.

Expand into a broader project titled “90 Days of School Health” covering topics such as sleep, light exercise, spinal care, nutrition, and stress reduction.

All hypertext links and section bookmarks will be removed from papers during the processing of papers for publication. If you need to refer to an Internet email address or URL in your paper, you must type out the address or URL fully in Regular font.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research team would like to express their most sincere gratitude to the individuals and organizations who supported

and provided favorable conditions for the successful completion of the scientific and technical project, *“The ‘Golden Posture - Bright Eyes’ Flashcard Set guiding correct sitting posture and protecting vision for secondary school students”*.

We extend our deep appreciation to:

1. The Board of Directors of Nguyen Trai Secondary School for providing the necessary facilities and time for the research team to deploy the large-scale pedagogical experiment.

2. The supervising teachers who offered enthusiastic support in product design, implementing research methods, and statistical data analysis.

3. The 191 students from grades 7 and 8 of Nguyen Trai Secondary School, who actively participated in the 28-day trial and provided valuable empirical data.

4. The specialists, medical doctors, and Medical Council who provided standardized information regarding correct studying posture and vision protection, particularly through referencing official guidelines from the Ministry of Health and the Central Eye Hospital.

5. The graphic design tools and statistical software (including Canva, Gemini, ChatGPT, and AI) that assisted the team in Flashcard design and data processing.

This support and trust have been a great motivation, helping the project confirm its scientific and practical significance.

REFERENCES

1. Ministry of Health. (2024). Vietnam School Health Report.
2. Ministry of Education and Training. (2018). Natural Science Textbook Grade 8.
3. Ministry of Education and Training. (2020). Eye Care and Blindness Prevention.
4. Trinh, M. P. (2024). The situation of scoliosis in primary school students in Thai Nguyen and the effectiveness of several intervention solutions (Doctoral dissertation).
5. Hoang, H. K. (2017). Study on refractive errors and intervention models in lower secondary school students in Da Nang city (Doctoral dissertation).
6. Muñoz-Álvarez, M., et al. (2024). Validation of CVS-Q teen for digital eye strain in adolescents. *Journal of Ophthalmology Research*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11405871/>
7. Oakley, P. A., et al. (2024). Assessment of forward head posture: Photogrammetry and symptom correlation in school-aged children. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopedics*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36977430/>
8. Nguyen, H. T. L., et al. (2025). Impact of spectacle use on academic performance among secondary schoolchildren in Vietnam. *PLoS ONE*, 20(5),

- e0322534. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0322534>
9. Tran, X. M. T., et al. (2025). Factors protecting against progression of myopia in school students exposed to societal change in Vietnam: A 3-year cohort study. *BMJ Open*, 15(1), e085853. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/15/1/e085853>
 10. Aykutlu, M. Ş., et al. (2024). Digital media use and its effects on digital eye strain and sleep quality in adolescents: A new emerging epidemic? *PLoS One*, 19(12), e0314390. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39700093>
 11. Kaur, K., et al. (2022). Digital eye strain – A comprehensive review. PMC. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9434525/>
 12. Verma, S., et al. (2018). Prevalence of forward head posture among 12–16-year-old school-going students—A cross-sectional study. *Applied Medical Research*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Prevalence-of-forward-head-posture-among-12-16-year-Verma-Shaikh/59da569e955a3752c48cc6a191fd7882782>
 13. Calvo, S., et al. (2025). Benefits of musculoskeletal health promotion in school environments. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/279e/c65b25f5fda9883def9cbeb445a89e70bd39.pdf>
 14. Gushgari, O. A., et al. (2024). Digital eye strain syndrome among higher education health sciences students in Saudi Arabia: Severity and preventive ergonomic practices. *PeerJ*, 12, e18423. <https://peerj.com/articles/18423/>
 15. Saeed, A., et al. (2024). Prevalence of forward head posture and its association with neck pain among school-going children. *Pakistan BMJ*, 7(5), e1141. <https://pakistanbmj.com/journal/index.php/pbmj/article/view/1141>
 16. Tran, X. M. T., et al. (2025). Prevalence of refractive errors in Vietnamese school children. *PubMed*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40889407/>
 17. Maiti, R., et al. (2025). Eye exercises are effective in managing digital eye strain among school students in selected higher secondary schools, West Bengal: Quasi-experimental study. *The Academic*, 3(7). <https://theacademic.in/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/134.pdf>